

Ghosts Behind the Walls: Kowloon Walled City in the Audiovisual Imagination and the Rewriting of Cultural Memory

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The City That Refused to Disappear: Kowloon Between Memory and Myth

In 1944, George Orwell wrote for *Tribune* magazine: “history is written by the victors, but time gives voice to the defeated.” This idea, previously suggested by Winston Churchill, reflects the extent to which human history is characterized by the reaffirmation of the present through a selective and instrumentalized memory. However, it is not necessary to go too far back in time to find a phenomenon of memocide or the reconstruction of social memory.

Between March 1993 and April 1994, the government of Hong Kong demolished Kowloon Walled City, an anarchic contemporary dystopia known as the City of Darkness and considered one of the most miserable and unsanitary vestiges of civilization in contemporary history. Today, very little remains of this city beyond several hundred photographs, a few interviews, and some documentary footage. Most of these historical sources are preserved in the documentary *City of Darkness: Life in Kowloon Walled City*, produced by Lambot and Girard in 1993.

However, cinema, anime, and video games have all created their own interpretations of Kowloon, contributing to the construction of the vanished walled city within the collective imagination. The award-winning video game *Stray* develops a dystopian narrative set in a fictional environment called The Neon City, clearly inspired by Kowloon. The recreation is so accurate that even former residents of the Walled City have recognized their old home in the game, as reported in the feature *Former Kowloon Walled City Resident Reacts to STRAY!* by Goldthread (November 29, 2022).

The fact that a fictional work can draw inspiration from a real city for which very few audiovisual records remain (Harter, 2000) revives the debate about the gap between cinematic and audiovisual imaginaries (Durand, 2004) and historical reality.

Although some aesthetic and symbolic approaches are consistent with Kowloon's historical and documentary legacy—such as neon lights, cramped spaces, and artistic inspirations associated with cyberpunk—other representations appear to be based on elements that generate a certain narrative heterotopia (May, 2022; Vidal-Mestre & Freire-Sánchez, 2023) and historical distortion. This phenomenon occurs when there is no correspondence between the historical legacy and the sociological or urban reality of the place and its fictionalized representation (Hetherington, 1997). In this regard, *Stray* presents an apocalyptic world inhabited only by intelligent robots, cats, and a kind of alien bacteria that has destroyed almost all forms of life. This recreation, inspired by Kowloon, is fictional, unrealistic, and anachronistic in relation to the city's actual history, yet it is easily accepted because it belongs to the realm of science fiction and does not attempt to reproduce reality faithfully. However, there are numerous films and video games that have supposedly tried to portray the reality of Kowloon more directly. Films such as *Bloodsport*, *Crime Story*, and the anime *Street Fighter II*, as well as video games such as *Shenmue II*, *Sleeping Dogs*, and *Call of Duty: Black Ops*, are among the many and varied representations of the Walled City.

To this end, the aim of this article is, through discourse analysis and the coding of results, to determine whether there is a relationship between the historical and documentary records of Kowloon and the different images projected through cinema, anime, and video games. The article therefore explores the contrasts between representations of Kowloon Walled City across different media and its documented reality. This comparison will be carried out especially through the documentary *City of Darkness: Life in Kowloon Walled City* (Lambot & Girard, 1993) and the documentary *Kowloon Walled City 1980* by journalists Christian Cascio and Marc Boulet, who managed to walk through the city with a video camera and gain access to illegal casinos, brothels, houses, and businesses. In this way, the study seeks to determine whether a narrative asynchrony has emerged between fiction and reality and to examine the historical legacy of the ecosystem in which more than 50,000 people coexisted in barely 26,000 square meters.

Inside the City of Darkness: Life, Chaos, and Community

Although today it is simply a park and no trace remains of what life was actually like in this historical enclave, Kowloon Walled City was a political and economic anarchy made up of a dense complex of buildings attached to Hong Kong. The anomalous pseudo-city began to take shape in 1898.

At first, it lacked basic infrastructure and essential services such as water, gas, and electricity, although this did not prevent residents from finding alternative ways to obtain these resources. For decades, it became a refuge for immigrants, fugitives, and other marginalized groups. The city eventually became a symbol of extreme poverty and precarious living conditions. It also became famous for having one of the highest population densities per square meter in the world. Specifically, it occupied an area of only 25,300 square meters (2.53 hectares), and although there are no exact figures—because many residents were not registered and lived anonymously or as fugitives—some sources (Harter, 2000; Nufrio, 2015; Fraser & Li, 2017; Quiroga, 2021) estimate that around 50,000 people lived there during the 1980s, the city’s demographic peak. This meant that Kowloon had roughly 125 times the population density of some of the world’s largest cities, such as Shanghai, Tokyo, or Delhi. The original design of Kowloon Walled City dates back to the seventeenth century, when it functioned as a defensive fort protecting the population from raiders who regularly attacked the coastal areas of Hong Kong during China’s Ming dynasty. By the end of the nineteenth century, the city had been fortified with walls and towers, gradually transforming into an urban settlement and, over time, into a labyrinth of alleys and buildings up to fourteen stories high. This height represented the only architectural limit imposed on the city, since taller buildings would have interfered with air traffic in Hong Kong. As a result, Kowloon expanded horizontally, creating overlapping substructures that blocked natural light and plunged the streets and most residences into darkness. For this reason, it became known as the City Without Light, although because of the countless fluorescent lights that remained on day and night, it was also nicknamed the City of Neon.

This urban and demographic expansion intensified especially during the second half of the twentieth century. The area became a poor and overcrowded district filled with deteriorating buildings, piles of rubbish, and rats, a reality that lasted until its demolition. As the area deteriorated, it became a dangerous and problematic place dominated by criminal gangs that plunged the city into fear and chaos. In this sense, Quiroga argues that “the work of Girard and Lambot shows us the most social side of a lawless space organized within its own chaos” (2021, p. 474).

Ultimately, it was the triads—Chinese organized crime groups—that came to dominate the territory, imposing their own authority and creating a kind of order within the chaos. As can be seen in the documentary by Cascio and Boulet, the triads controlled illegal businesses such as counterfeit Swiss watches, gambling, prostitution, and protection rackets imposed on local shops.

The fact that all commerce, transactions, and streets were regulated by the triads allowed for a certain degree of safety, as long as residents obeyed their rules, since they kept rival gangs and criminals away.

Despite this dimension, the Walled City was also home to thousands of people who lived humbly and had no involvement in illegal activities or the triads (Nufrio, 2015). This can be seen in the various documentaries produced during the 1980s and 1990s. In the documentary by Cascio and Boulet, for example, children can be seen playing in the streets, homes remaining open at all hours, and shops and street stalls operating continuously.

Daily life, although marked by deplorable and inhuman living conditions, continued with a certain sense of safety and freedom, as stated by Albert Ng, a former resident of Kowloon, in *Goldthread* (November 29, 2022). Kowloon's inhabitants created a community and adapted to these conditions (Nufrio, 2015).

In this regard, Quiroga argues that Kowloon was a community and structure that made life possible for its residents by "providing everything from water supply to social services, religion, and care for the elderly and children" (2021, p. 477).

Nevertheless, as shown in both documentaries, the streets also contained drug users, dead animals, and a nearly omnipresent atmosphere of darkness and dirt. These factors, combined with Hong Kong's modernization and pressure from international organizations, ultimately led to Kowloon's demolition between 1993 and 1994.

Ironically, although residents were financially compensated so that they could rebuild their lives elsewhere, many resisted leaving Kowloon because, despite everything, it was still their home.

Mapping the Imagined City: Methods for Comparing Fiction and History

In order to compare the fictional representation of Kowloon Walled City in films, series, anime, and video games with its documented historical reality, an initial audiovisual search was carried out across these media, together with the available documentaries devoted to the city.

This search produced a total of seventeen relevant cases: six films, two anime series, and nine video games.

Once the sources had been identified and coded, a content analysis was conducted, paying particular attention to the fictional representation of Kowloon Walled City and to the living conditions, daily life, and social environment of its inhabitants.

Content analysis was selected because it "allows comparative studies to be carried out between different documents or reference objects, as well as between different sources or periods" (Bernete, 2014, p. 194). This methodology makes it possible to compare recurring themes, symbolic elements, aesthetic resources, and narrative structures across different media while identifying similarities and divergences with the documented reality of Kowloon.

The analysis focused especially on the following dimensions:

1. The architectural representation of Kowloon, including density, verticality, darkness, alleyways, neon lights, and the general urban atmosphere.
2. The representation of its inhabitants, including their appearance, occupations, routines, and living conditions.
3. The presence of organized crime, violence, poverty, prostitution, gambling, and illegal businesses.
4. The symbolic and aesthetic relationship between Kowloon and genres such as cyberpunk, dystopia, horror, and science fiction.
5. The degree of realism or distortion in relation to the historical and documentary record.

Finally, the results of the content analysis were contrasted with the theories of narrative heterotopia and cultural alteration, taking as their principal point of reference the documentaries *Kowloon Walled City 1980* and *City of Darkness: Life in Kowloon Walled City*.

These documentaries are particularly valuable because they include direct footage of the city before its demolition, showing streets, homes, businesses, illegal casinos, brothels, and the daily life of its inhabitants. They therefore provide a useful documentary basis for determining the extent to which fictional representations remain faithful to the historical reality of Kowloon or, on the contrary, transform it into a symbolic, exaggerated, or distorted space.

This comparison seeks to answer the following research questions:

RQ1. Has the fictional recreation of Kowloon in films, anime series, and video games created a specific audiovisual imaginary?

RQ2. Is there cultural and historical distortion in the recreation of Kowloon Walled City?

RQ3. Does a narrative heterotopia emerge in these fictional reproductions?

From Ruins to Neon Dreams: Kowloon in Popular Culture

Kowloon, famous for its unique architecture and urban design, became a recurring subject in popular culture. For decades, it inspired both fear and fascination among the citizens of Hong Kong. Over time, this fascination spread to other cultures and was reflected in various artistic expressions and entertainment media. Its unique appearance and architecture have inspired many fictional works, including video games, which seek to recreate its dystopian, decaying atmosphere and the architectural complexity of the vanished city. In particular, video games are especially relevant because of their capacity to digitally reconstruct places from the past (Venegas, 2018).

In addition to its architecture and atmosphere of decay, the omnipresence of the Chinese mafia—operating with relative impunity due to the inability of the police and judicial system to intervene effectively—helped to create the legend of a lawless city, ideal for inspiring countless audiovisual productions. One of the earliest examples of this influence is *Blade Runner*, which drew allegorical inspiration from Kowloon’s atmosphere and contributed greatly to the iconic relationship between the city and the cyberpunk movement (Kwok & Coppoolse, 2018). Although not located in Asia, the film reproduces many of the elements that have come to define the cultural imaginary of Kowloon: neon lights, overcrowding, and narrow, wet, dark alleyways.

Later, *Bloodsport*, starring Jean-Claude Van Damme, recreated part of Kowloon as the setting for an underground fighting tournament controlled by the triads. The city is presented as a dark, dirty place filled with violence and criminality. Another example is *Ready Player One*, which, like *Blade Runner*, recreates a dystopian environment inspired by Kowloon (Palomo Beltrán & Reséndiz Vázquez, 2022). Similarly, iconic fictional cities such as Gotham City, from the Batman universe, have also drawn inspiration from Kowloon’s claustrophobic, dark, and oppressive atmosphere, as well as from the presence of criminal gangs operating beyond the reach of the police. In anime, Kowloon has also been a constant source of inspiration. In the episode “Darkness at Kowloon Palace” from the anime adaptation of *Street Fighter II*, protagonists Ken and Ryu enter the Walled City to confront some of the region’s most dangerous criminals and underground fighters.

As for video games, many titles have represented Kowloon, whether through architectural design, references to its lifestyle, or allegorical and metaphorical recreations such as *Stray*. *Shenmue II* recreates a large part of the city, allowing players, through the protagonist Ryo Hazuki, to wander through its streets and experience its atmosphere firsthand. Other examples include *Call of Duty: Black Ops*, which features a level inspired by Kowloon in 1968, and *Sleeping Dogs*, which includes a fictionalized section of Kowloon within its explorable map.

These and many other examples recreate the cultural imaginary of a disappeared city for which very few audiovisual records remain. As a result, fictional recreations may gradually replace historical records and become the dominant references.

As Sabine (2013) argues in her study of how South African memory is projected in other continents, not enough attention has been paid to cultural differences in the ways societies remember. In this sense, Kowloon may eventually be remembered more for its influence on audiovisual culture than for the reality experienced by its inhabitants.

Under these premises, this article compares real and documented representations of Kowloon Walled City with fictional representations in films and video games, analyzing the differences in terms of citizens, culture, and lifestyle. In doing so, it seeks to determine whether these cultural imaginaries reproduce reality or, on the

contrary, distort it by emphasizing some elements and omitting others, thus generating a form of historical and cultural alteration.

Neon Shadows and Empty Streets: How Media Recreated Kowloon

The audiovisual search identified a wide range of works from different media, formats, and genres. Video games were the most frequent medium, with a total of nine titles either directly representing or clearly inspired by Kowloon Walled City. Six films and two anime productions were also identified.

Video games are particularly significant because their immersive and exploratory mechanics allow players to inspect the city in greater detail, including its architecture, atmosphere, and the living conditions of its inhabitants.

Overall, the analysis revealed three main representational trends: realistic recreations, futuristic reinterpretations, and allegorical appropriations.

The first trend includes works that attempt to reproduce Kowloon's urban layout, density, and social environment with some degree of fidelity. The clearest example is *Shenmue II*, which recreates much of the city with remarkable detail. Through the protagonist Ryo Hazuki, the player can move through narrow corridors, staircases, shops, apartments, and rooftops, gaining a sense of both the vertical and horizontal complexity of the Walled City. Unlike most representations, *Shenmue II* also includes civilians, children, shopkeepers, and ordinary residents, giving visibility to the daily life that characterized Kowloon.

Another example is *Crime Story*, which was filmed in Kowloon shortly before its demolition. Although the film focuses heavily on crime and police corruption, it also includes local businesses, residential areas, and the contrast between the presence of ordinary residents and the influence of the triads. These two works are the only cases in the sample that do not significantly distort the documented reality of Kowloon.

By contrast, many of the other representations reduce Kowloon to a space defined almost exclusively by violence, criminality, and decay. *Bloodsport*, *Stranglehold*, the anime episode "Darkness at Kowloon Palace" from *Street Fighter II*, and *Call of Duty: Black Ops* all emphasize gang activity, underground combat, or extreme violence, while almost completely omitting the daily lives of ordinary residents.

A recurring pattern in these works is the emptiness of the streets and buildings. In many cases, the city appears devoid of families, children, elderly people, local commerce, or any sign of normal community life. This omission is especially striking given that Kowloon was one of the most densely populated places in human history.

This selective focus not only alters the historical and cultural image of the city, but also produces a form of narrative heterotopia: a fictional version of Kowloon that is visually recognizable but sociologically implausible.

Other productions adopt a futuristic approach. *Deus Ex* and *Shadowrun: Hong Kong* reinterpret Kowloon as a cyberpunk dystopia. In these titles, the city becomes darker, more technologically advanced, and more labyrinthine than the documented reality. Although these works preserve some architectural features associated with Kowloon—such as narrow passageways, overcrowded structures, and omnipresent neon lights—they transform the city into a futuristic symbol of urban collapse.

Similarly, works such as *Blade Runner*, *Batman Begins*, *Ready Player One*, *Alita: Battle Angel*, and *Stray* do not reproduce Kowloon directly, but instead use selected elements of its architecture and atmosphere to build fictional cities.

Remembering the Unremembered: Kowloon Beyond Cyberpunk Fantasy

The findings allow the research questions to be answered clearly:

Regarding RQ1—whether the fictional recreation of Kowloon in films, anime, and video games has created a specific audiovisual imaginary—the answer is yes. Across the different media analyzed, Kowloon is consistently represented as a dark, lawless, overcrowded, violent, and dystopian environment. Certain recurring features appear repeatedly: narrow alleys, poor hygiene, criminal activity, neon lights, the absence of effective policing, and the omnipresence of organized crime. However, this imaginary is highly selective. Most works prioritize the most visually striking and narratively useful aspects of Kowloon, particularly those related to violence, decay, and criminality, while ignoring other dimensions of daily life.

Regarding RQ2—whether there is cultural and historical distortion in the recreation of Kowloon Walled City—the analysis indicates that only two of the seventeen works studied avoid a significant distortion of the city’s historical memory: *Crime Story* and *Shenmue II*. The remaining productions either present a highly fictionalized version of Kowloon or focus only on the elements that are most attractive for science fiction, action cinema, or video game design. One of the clearest distortions is the almost complete absence of children, families, workers, and ordinary residents. This omission is especially important because the documentaries clearly show that Kowloon was not only a space of criminality, but also a place where thousands of people built communities, opened businesses, raised children, and developed systems of coexistence.

Regarding RQ3—whether narrative heterotopia is produced in these fictional recreations—the results strongly suggest that it is. In most representations, Kowloon is shown as an empty city with deserted streets, abandoned apartments, and almost no civilian life. This is incompatible with the documented reality of the city as one of the most densely populated places in the world.

Likewise, many works portray Kowloon as technologically advanced or futuristic, despite the fact that the historical city lacked even basic infrastructure in many areas. These distortions generate a fictional space that borrows the visual identity of Kowloon while disconnecting it from its social, historical, and demographic reality.

Kowloon Walled City was undoubtedly a fascinating place, not because it was desirable, but because it represented a unique urban anomaly. Its darkness, narrow alleys, claustrophobic architecture, and unusual social order made it one of the most visually and culturally distinctive spaces of the twentieth century.

For this reason, it has become a recurring reference point in cyberpunk and dystopian aesthetics, influencing fictional cities such as the Los Angeles of *Blade Runner*, the Columbus of *Ready Player One*, or the Neon City of *Stray*.

Nevertheless, these representations should be understood as fictional constructions rather than accurate reconstructions of reality. They often reduce Kowloon to an environment of criminals, gangsters, and violence, ignoring the fact that thousands of people lived there peacefully, worked honestly, and developed forms of solidarity and coexistence despite the difficult conditions.

Ultimately, the study reveals a clear gap between documented reality and fictional representation. In the pursuit of dramatic atmosphere, post-apocalyptic aesthetics, and cyberpunk imagery, most audiovisual works contribute to a cultural and historical distortion of Kowloon, transforming a real place and its inhabitants into a myth of urban darkness.

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